

Catch me if you can: biodegradation of nanomaterials and advanced materials

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ABSTRACT

Biodegradation commonly refers to the breakdown of organic matter by microorganisms. However, the term biodegradation has recently been usurped by the nano (bio)technology community with reference to the biological (enzymatic) degradation of nanomaterials and other advanced materials. Here we address the degradation or dissolution of nanomaterials and advanced materials including graphene-based materials and other emerging two-dimensional (2D) materials in the body and in the natural environment. Understanding the degradation profile of nanomaterials and advanced materials is relevant for the clinical use of such materials.

1. Nanomaterials and other advanced materials

Engineered nanomaterials (ENMs) are generally defined as intentionally produced materials with at least one dimension between 1 and 100 nm [1]. ENMs display properties that differ from the bulk form of the same material. From a toxicological point of view, two features distinguish nanomaterials from their larger counterparts [2]. First, surface area and surface reactivity are greater (per mass) for smaller particles when compared to bigger particles. Second, small particles are able to negotiate biological barriers, thereby giving rise to unanticipated effects, i.e., effects not anticipated based on studies of bigger particles of the same composition [2]. Advanced materials, in turn, are “materials that are rationally designed to have new or enhanced properties, and/or targeted or enhanced structural features with the objective to achieve specific or improved functional performance” [3]. The latter ‘working description’ of advanced materials also clarifies that advanced materials need not be limited to the nanoscale. However, ENMs including two-dimensional (2D) materials may fall under the scope of advanced materials. For an overview of the various materials and their applications, the reader is referred to other recent reviews [4–8]. The present review aims to address the nexus between engineered nanomaterials/advanced materials and biological systems [9], with particular focus on the degradation or dissolution of man-made materials in the body and the environment.

2. Nanomaterials are prone to biotransformation

Nanomaterials are dynamic entities insofar as they are prone to undergo various transformations in biological systems [10]. This process, sometimes referred to as ‘aging’ of nanomaterials [11], may drastically influence the interplay between nanomaterials and the environment. There is a significant amount of information on the biodurability (or solubility) of conventional particles and fibers and its implications for toxicological outcomes (see Ref. [12] for a recent overview). Here we will focus on carbon-based nanomaterials including single- and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNTs) as well as graphene-based materials (GBMs), along with other emerging 2D materials such as transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), transition metal carbides and nitrides (collectively referred to as MXenes), and other advanced materials including hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) and black phosphorous (BP). We will discuss the degradation and/or dissolution of these materials in mammalian model systems as well as biotic and abiotic degradation in the environment. Finally, we will address the relevance of biodegradation (or biopersistence) with respect to medical applications.

3. Enzymatic (bio)degradation of carbon nanotubes

Horseradish has been cultivated since antiquity, and horseradish peroxidase (HRP), found in the plant, is used extensively in molecular biology. The first example of enzymatic degradation of CNTs was

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provided in 2008 when Allen et al. [13] reported that single-walled CNTs underwent degradation over a period of several weeks as a result of the oxidative activity of HRP and low concentrations of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). Further evidence of peroxidase-catalyzed degradation of CNTs was furnished in a follow-up study [14]. The authors could show that while carboxylated CNTs were degraded, pristine CNTs were impervious to biodegradation with HRP and H_2O_2 . In another seminal study, human neutrophil-derived myeloperoxidase (MPO) was found to 'digest' single-walled CNTs; moreover, *in vitro* digested CNTs did not evoke pulmonary inflammation when aspirated into mice [15]. MPO is known to bind to negatively charged molecules, including phosphatidylserine (PS), and PS, in turn, has been shown to tag CNTs for engulfment by professional phagocytes [16]. Using pristine, carboxylated, phospholipid (PS or PC)-coated, and immunoglobulin-functionalized CNTs, the authors highlighted the role of surface charge and functionalization for the degradation profile of CNTs [15]. In a companion study, the oxidation and clearance of single-walled CNTs from the lungs of MPO knockout mice was found to be considerably less effective when compared to wild-type mice [17]. The latter findings thus provided compelling evidence for the *in vivo* degradation of CNTs. Overall, while certain multi-walled CNTs seem to emulate asbestos with respect to *in vivo* pathogenicity [18], CNTs are not biopersistent and therefore not 'asbestos-like'.

Following these pioneering studies, a plethora of other studies on the biodegradation of CNTs have been published [19], and the repertoire of peroxidases has expanded from HRP and MPO to EPO (eosinophil

peroxidase) [20] and LPO (lactoperoxidase) [21] (Fig. 1). Degradation of CNTs has also been observed in mildly oxidizing phagolysosomal simulant fluid (PSF) over a period of 90 days, but unmodified (non-carboxylated) CNTs did not undergo degradation, in accordance with previous work [22]. Furthermore, multi-walled CNTs were found to undergo degradation in response to HRP although not as effectively when compared to single-walled CNTs [23,24]. However, surface modification of multi-walled CNTs with functional substrates was shown to enhance the HRP-dependent biodegradation of these materials [25]. In a key study, other investigators attempted to determine the half-life of CNTs. To this end, the authors incubated 13 different types of CNTs with HRP using established protocols, and reasoned that the analytical methods commonly employed for studying the degradation of CNTs did not have the sensitivity needed to ascertain their half-life [26]. To obtain a better understanding of the biodegradation of CNTs, the authors deployed radiolabeled CNTs, and found that CO_2 evolved linearly at a rate of about 0.02 % per day. Thus, they concluded that the CNTs were oxidized by HRP, albeit very slowly [26].

Interestingly, neutrophils were found to be capable of degrading CNTs functionalized with poly (ethylene) glycol (PEG), and MPO-generated hypochlorous acid (HOCl) was implicated as the major oxidant responsible for the degradation of PEG-CNTs [27]. Subsequent studies provided evidence for a two-step process of neutrophil elastase (NE)-dependent 'stripping' (defunctionalization) and MPO-dependent degradation of PEG-CNTs [28]. Moreover, neutrophils were shown to 'capture' single-walled CNTs in neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs),

Fig. 1. Enzymatic degradation. Human enzymes are capable of degrading carbon-based nanomaterials, exemplified here by carbon nanotubes (CNTs). The enzymes depicted are myeloperoxidase (MPO) and eosinophil peroxidase (EPO), expressed in neutrophils and eosinophils, respectively, and lactoperoxidase (LPO), a related peroxidase that is secreted by epithelial cells into the airways. Furthermore, it is speculated here that vascular peroxidase 1 (VPO1) (also known as peroxidasin), an enzyme that is secreted into the blood stream by vascular endothelial cells, might be capable of digesting nanomaterials, though this remains to be proven experimentally. Finally, the inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) in macrophages and other cell types is deployed to achieve NO-dependent degradation in various anatomical compartments. The protein structures were derived from the Protein Data Bank in Europe Knowledge Base (PDBE-KB), part of the ELIXIR data resources infrastructure.

web-like structures of chromatin studded with MPO and other granule proteins, leading to the extracellular degradation of CNTs [29].

Using a panel of 11 carbon-based materials encompassing single-walled and multi-walled CNTs, along with carbon nanohorns (CNHs), the acellular degradation in sodium hypochlorite (colloquially known as household bleach) was evaluated [30]. The authors concluded that the degradation rate was largely dependent on the diameter of the CNTs. In another comparative study, the authors addressed a set of materials including graphene oxide (GO), multi-walled CNTs, and CNHs, and found that GO was more rapidly degraded [31]. These simplified protocols provide useful insights regarding the properties that dictate the degradability of carbonaceous nanomaterials.

However, from a physiological (and toxicological) point of view, the discovery that cells of the innate immune system, most notably neutrophils, are capable of 'digesting' carbon nanotubes is an important milestone [32]. Neutrophils, the most abundant white blood cell in the circulation, are first responders at sites of infection and inflammation [33]. On the other hand, neutrophils are short-lived cells, whereas macrophages are tissue-resident cells tasked with restoring tissue homeostasis through the clearance of cell debris. Another important milestone is the discovery that macrophages can 'digest' CNTs [34,35]. In contrast to neutrophils, which contain cytoplasmic granules loaded with MPO, macrophages do not express significant amounts of MPO. Instead, evidence was provided for a peroxynitrite-driven oxidative pathway of biodegradation [34,35]. This pathway is premised on the cooperation between two key enzymes in macrophages, NADPH oxidase, which produces superoxide, and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), which produces nitric oxide (NO). These radicals then react to form peroxynitrite [34]. The latter studies were both performed using human THP-1 cells as a model of macrophages [34,35]. Degradation of multi-walled CNTs was also observed in the murine macrophage-like cell line RAW264.7, with evidence for an intracellular pH-dependent mechanism [36]. CNHs were also found to undergo degradation in THP-1 and RAW264.7 cell lines [37]. Using a murine chondrocyte cell line (ATDC-5), NO-dependent biodegradation of PEG-CNTs was demonstrated, and biodegradation in the cartilage of mice following intraarticular injection of PEG-CNTs was also observed [38].

4. Biodegradation of graphene-based materials

Early work revealed that HRP catalyzed the oxidation of graphene oxide (GO) resulting in holes in the GO sheets, while reduced GO (rGO) was not susceptible to degradation [39]. Subsequent studies showed that GO was degraded by recombinant MPO [40] as well as in the presence of primary human neutrophils activated to release MPO [41]. Moreover, GO sheets were found to provoke specific changes in the lipid composition of the plasma membrane of neutrophils resulting in the release of NETs [42]. GO sheets also underwent MPO-dependent degradation in purified NETs [41]. Other investigators confirmed that GO elicited size-dependent effects in neutrophils [43]. Graphene itself is also degraded by primary human neutrophils albeit not as rapidly as GO. Hence, few-layer graphene (FLG) was found to undergo degradation after co-incubation for 5 days with neutrophils, as evidenced by confocal Raman mapping [44].

Using zebrafish as a model, GO was shown to undergo NO-dependent biodegradation [45]. Hence, degradation was blocked upon knockdown of iNOS or by pharmacological inhibition of iNOS using L-NAME, providing unequivocal evidence for NO-dependent degradation of GO in a living organism. Moreover, by using the transgenic strain Tg (*mpx*: eGFP) to visualize and track neutrophils in zebrafish, the authors could show that inhibition of the degradation of GO resulted in increased neutrophil infiltration into the gastrointestinal tract. In other words, biodegradation of GO mitigated inflammation.

In another intriguing study, GBMs incubated up to 14 days in human plasma were found to undergo biotransformation, resulting in the formation of holes and wrinkles in the basal plane with further

decomposition to small molecules (aromatic hydrocarbons) [46]. The authors performed exhaustive characterization of the GBMs, and reasoned that "active substances" (e.g., hydroxyl radicals or superoxide anions) were responsible for the biotransformation though the mechanism was not revealed. It is worth noting that vascular peroxidase 1 (VPO1), the mammalian homologue of the insect peroxidase peroxidase, can use exogenous H₂O₂ or H₂O₂ generated from co-expressed NADPH oxidase to catalyze peroxidase reactions; indeed, the enzymatic properties and substrate specificities of VPO1 are similar to MPO [47,48]. Perhaps VPO1 is responsible for the biotransformation of nanomaterials in the vascular system.

In a recent study, 11 different 2D materials including different GBMs as well as hBN, MoS₂ and WS₂, were subjected to a simulated 3-phase (oral, gastric, and intestinal) digestion to replicate the biotransformation that may occur after ingestion [49]. The 2D materials were dispersed using sodium cholate (a non-ionic, non-denaturing detergent) or Pluronic® F-108 (a non-ionic copolymer surfactant). The authors noted significant agglomeration of all materials upon simulated digestion, most prominently for graphene, and they found that MoS₂ had dissolved by 75 % by the end of the digestion.

Girish et al. [50] provided first evidence of *in vivo* degradation of GBMs following i.v. injection in mice. The authors applied confocal Raman imaging to evaluate the degradation of graphene over a period of 3 months, and they deduced that tissue-resident macrophages played a major role, though the mechanism was not disclosed. However, it is plausible that NO-dependent mechanisms may come into play (see below). Other investigators demonstrated that GO sheets undergo degradation in macrophages in the spleen over a period of 9 months following i.v. injection in mice [51]. Moreover, GO was found to translocate to the brain upon intranasal exposure in mice, and microglia (tissue-resident macrophages of the central nervous system) were implicated in the degradation of GO over a period of one month [52]. In a more recent study, the biodegradation or biopersistence of a panel of GBMs was evaluated up to 28 days after pharyngeal aspiration in mice [53]. The authors observed that neutrophils recruited to the lungs of mice internalized and degraded small GO sheets faster than macrophages while large GO sheets remained unscathed within macrophages. Overall, it appeared that small GBMs (<1 μm) were degraded and eliminated more efficiently than 'large' materials with lateral dimensions exceeding 5 μm [53]. In another seminal study, hepatic degradation of FLG was documented, and evidence for a novel mechanism involving erythrophagocytosis by Kupffer cells (tissue-resident macrophages of the liver) was provided [54]. The authors found that FLG, when intravenously injected into mice, caused hemolysis of red blood cells, whereupon the damaged red blood cells were phagocytosed by Kupffer cells. This resulted in the dysregulation of iron homeostasis due to the degradation of hemoglobin. FLG also promoted the expression of hepcidin, a key regulator of the cellular uptake of iron. The accumulation of iron triggered the Fenton reaction, and FLG sheets were subsequently transformed to CO₂ by the hydroxyl radicals generated via the Fenton reaction [54]. Taken together, these studies testify to the remarkable capacity of the immune system in terms of handling not only offending microorganisms but nanomaterials as well [55].

Graphdiyne oxide (GDYO), the oxidized form of graphdiyne, a 2D allotrope of carbon distinct from graphene, was recently shown to undergo biodegradation in primary human macrophages [56]. Notably, degradation was observed in M1-polarized macrophages, characterized by high expression of iNOS, but not in M2-polarized macrophages. The peroxynitrite-driven degradation of GDYO was corroborated in an acellular system using the peroxynitrite donor, SIN-1. Moreover, secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines was dependent on biodegradation. Hence, IL-1β secretion was triggered in M1 macrophages upon exposure to GDYO, while this was abolished in the presence of the iNOS inhibitor, L-NAME, and the NADPH oxidase inhibitor, DPI [56]. Other investigators provided evidence for the biotransformation of GDYO into graphdiyne quantum dots (GDQDs) following i.p. injection in mice, and

this was recapitulated by incubating GDYO *in vitro* in the presence of sodium hypochlorite [57].

5. Biodegradation of other emerging 2D materials

Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) are a class of layered inorganic compounds with the chemical composition MX_2 , where M is a transition metal such as tungsten or molybdenum, and X is a chalcogen such as sulfur, selenium, or tellurium. TMDs may be viewed as inorganic analogues of graphene, endowed with many favorable mechanical and electronic properties, and MoS_2 is the most studied TMD to date [58].

Dissolution of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles is well established, and particular focus has been devoted to the intracellular ion release elicited by the acidic milieu of the lysosomal compartment [59]. It is plausible that transition metal-based 2D materials such as MoS_2 might evoke toxicity through intra- or extracellular release of ions, and dissolution screening in biological or environmental media has been proposed as a logical first step in the hazard assessment of emerging (metallic) 2D materials [60–62].

Furthermore, beyond the oxidation or ‘aging’ of TMDs under ambient conditions [63], it may also be relevant to ask whether such materials are susceptible to enzymatic degradation. Early work suggested that MoS_2 nanosheets were resistant to enzymatic degradation when tested up to 30 days; however, the MoS_2 nanosheets were degraded in the presence of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) alone [64]. In contrast, using MoS_2 nanosheets modified with polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), an amphiphilic polymer, other investigators found that exposure to H_2O_2 alone led to partial degradation whereas MPO combined with a physiological amount of H_2O_2 resulted in the rapid and near-complete degradation of MoS_2 [65]. The authors also applied X-ray absorption near-edge structure (XANES) to ascertain the chemical species of molybdenum. Upon exposure to $\text{MPO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ for 30 days, MoS_2 -PVP was almost completely oxidized from Mo(IV) to Mo(VI), primarily in the form of soluble molybdate ions (MoO_4^{2-}) [65]. Finally, the authors administered MoS_2 -PVP to mice *via* intravenous (i.v.), intraperitoneal (i.p.), and intragastric (i.g.) administration routes. Following i.v. injection, nanosheets displayed noticeable clearance due to the decreased accumulation in the liver and spleen within 30 days when compared with the i.p. administration route, for which a slight accumulation of MoS_2 -PVP in the spleen was observed. After i.g. administration, the nanosheets accumulated in gastrointestinal organs and were excreted within 48 h. Other investigators explored the biodistribution of PEGylated MoS_2 , WS_2 , and TiS_2 nanosheets in mice [66]. Notably, all three materials displayed a predominant accumulation in the liver and spleen after i.v. injection. However, in marked contrast to WS_2 -PEG and TiS_2 -PEG, which showed significant accumulation in these organs for months, MoS_2 -PEG was found to be degraded and excreted almost completely within one month [66]. The tungsten content in the liver actually increased over time in mice injected with WS_2 -PEG, owing to the gradual translocation of WS_2 -PEG from the spleen to the liver. Further studies confirmed that each TMD displayed a distinct degradation or transformation behavior. MoS_2 -PEG underwent oxidation upon storage in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), resulting in a transparent solution attributed to the formation of soluble Mo(VI) species, whereas WS_2 -PEG, with its strong W–S bonds and superior chemical stability, exhibited minimal degradation, thus explaining its prolonged biological retention. Meanwhile, the poor excretability of TiS_2 -PEG was suggested to be due to its biotransformation into insoluble TiO_2 aggregates [66]. These studies [65,66] both serve as an important reference for *in vivo* applications of TMDs.

Most biodegradation studies have focused on peroxidases, but other pathways may exist. Cao et al. [67] found that MoS_2 complexed with human serum albumin (HSA) was sequestered by macrophages in the liver and spleen following i.v. injection in mice. XANES demonstrated that MoS_2 was oxidized in the liver, with molybdenum being chemically transformed from Mo(IV) to Mo(VI), and the authors reasoned that

cytochrome P450 enzymes, the main oxidases in liver microsomes, contributed to the oxidation of MoS_2 [67]. On the other hand, carbon-based ENMs inhibit CYP450s [68,69], and CYP450-dependent oxidation of such materials therefore seems unlikely.

MXenes (transition metal carbides and nitrides) are inorganic 2D materials with the general formula $\text{M}_{n+1}\text{X}_n\text{T}_x$, where M is an early transition metal (most often titanium, niobium, vanadium, molybdenum, or tantalum), X represents carbon and/or nitrogen, and T_x refers to surface terminations of the outer metal layers, while n denotes the number of transition metal layers, and can take values from 1 to 4 [70]. Ti_2C_3 MXenes were first synthesized in 2011 using a so-called MAX phase as a precursor [71]. MXenes are named with reference to graphene, the very first 2D atomic crystal [72,73].

MXenes are versatile materials, but they are prone to degradation under ambient conditions, and this is thus a major drawback of MXenes [74]. In particular, ‘classical’ Ti_2C_3 MXenes are prone to oxidation in air and water, gradually transforming into TiO_2 . In recent years, a plethora of stabilizing agents was proposed to remedy this problem [74]. For instance, sodium L-ascorbate, an organic salt of ascorbic acid (vitamin C), was shown to prolong the shelf-life of Ti_2C_3 MXenes [75]. Moreover, glutathione (GSH), a natural antioxidant present in millimolar concentrations in cells, was found to provide superior protection of Ti_2C_3 MXenes while maintaining the biocompatibility of the materials [76]. Several studies have addressed the degradability of MXenes in the context of biomedical applications. Molybdenum- and tungsten-based MXenes were shown to undergo pH-dependent degradation (transformation) with rapid breakdown at basic pH while greater stability was observed in acidic environments mimicking the mildly acidic tumor microenvironment [77,78]. In the latter study, $\text{W}_{1.33}\text{C}$ MXenes were complexed with bovine serum albumin (BSA) to enhance the dispersibility and biocompatibility of the materials [78]. The authors observed rapid clearance in normal tissues in mice while the materials were retained in tumor tissues, and the $\text{W}_{1.33}\text{C}$ -BSA MXenes were successfully deployed as photothermal agents [78]. Similarly, PEG-modified tungsten nitride (PEG-WN) MXenes for combinatorial chemo-photothermal therapy were readily excreted in one week following i.v. injection in mice, and the MXenes were found to undergo oxidation from tungsten nitride to tungsten oxide [79]. When lateral dimensions of MXenes are less than 10 nm, these materials may exhibit quantum limiting effects, and the obtained quantum dots (QDs) are called MXene QDs. Several recent studies have documented the degradability of titanium- and non-titanium-based MXene QDs. Hence, the breakdown of Ti_2C_3 MXene QDs was observed in deionized water, PBS, and cell culture medium [80]. Ti_2N MXene QDs were also shown to undergo degradation in water over the course of 8 days, with titanium oxide and hydrogen titanium oxide the likely final degradation products [81]. Moreover, Nb_2C MXene QDs were found to undergo rapid degradation when incubated with $\text{MPO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ [82]. The authors found that the QDs remained structurally intact in PBS but gradually lost their architecture under oxidative conditions. Nb_2C MXenes functionalized with PVP showed a similar enzyme-sensitive degradation profile. Hence, upon incubation with $\text{MPO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$, complete degradation of the nanosheets was observed within 24 h [83]. Furthermore, 20 % of the Nb was excreted by 48 h post-intravenous injection in mice, but the authors did not address the mechanism of degradation or decomposition of the MXenes *in vivo* [83]. Nevertheless, the preclinical studies referenced here have provided evidence that MXene sheets and/or QDs could be safely exploited for photothermal cancer ablation.

Boron nitride nanotubes (BNNs) and hBN are structural analogues of CNTs and graphene, respectively; indeed, hBN is sometimes referred to as ‘white graphene’ [84]. However, unlike carbon-based nanomaterials, hBN was found to be resistant to HRP and poorly degraded by MPO [85]. On the other hand, hBN was susceptible to degradation *via* the photo-Fenton reaction [86], with complete oxidation within 100 h [85]. Test-tube experiments using recombinant peroxidases are useful for screening [87], but may not recapitulate the degradative potential of

primary cells. Indeed, using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) and confocal Raman imaging, Liu et al. [88] could show that hBN was “disrupted” (degraded) by human neutrophils. Released boron in the supernatant of the cultures was detected by using ICP-MS, confirming the degradation of hBN by neutrophils after a 36 h incubation. Thus, while hBN displays oxidation resistance under ambient conditions [89], it is evidently susceptible to degradation by hypochlorous acid (HOCl) generated by MPO. The partially degraded hBN sheets, but not the soluble (ionic) degradation products, were found to be more cytotoxic than the parental (non-degraded) materials [85]. Therefore, while hBN does not provoke inflammation [90], it is important to understand the propensity to undergo degradation to properly gauge the risk of exposure to hBN.

BP consists of stacked 2D layers of sp^3 -hybridized phosphorus atoms connected *via* interlayer weak van der Waals forces, much like graphite; in keeping with graphene, monolayer BP is referred to as ‘phosphorene’ [91]. The practical application of layered BP (LBP) is hampered by the rapid decomposition under ambient conditions. Zhang et al. [92] found that LBP degraded faster in alkaline solutions than in neutral or acidic solutions. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations showed that OH^- initiated the decomposition through breaking the P–P bond and forming a P–O bond. The authors applied ^{31}P nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy for the detection of hypophosphite ($H_2PO_2^-$), the degradation product of LBP generated from OH^- reacting with P atoms, thus confirming the hypothesis [92]. Capitalizing on the propensity to undergo degradation, others have demonstrated rapid intracellular degradation of BPs and acute elevation of phosphate anions in human cancer cell lines, accompanied by anti-proliferative effects, whereas non-cancerous cells were not affected [93]. The authors proposed that the selective anti-cancer effects of BP could be exploited as an anticancer therapy, and a subsequent *in vivo* study confirmed the anticancer potential (aka “bioactive phospho-therapy”) of BP [94]. In another notable study [95], BP QDs encapsulated within poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) were synthesized, and the authors provided evidence that the PLGA shell not only isolated the BP QDs from oxygen and water thereby enhancing their stability for photothermal (PTT) applications but also controlled the rate of degradation of the BP QDs. Thus, BP QD-based nanospheres combined biodegradability and biocompatibility with high PTT efficiency.

6. Environmental decomposition of nanomaterials

ENMs also undergo transformations in the environment. These transformations include physical and chemical transformations, biologically mediated transformations (biodegradation), and interactions with macromolecules (including corona formation) [96]. Carbonaceous nanomaterials such as buckminsterfullerenes, CNTs, and GO photo-transform when exposed to sunlight or UV light irradiation [97–101] leading to the formation of CO_2 and various other photoproducts including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). Moreover, indirect phototransformation can occur in natural water bodies where constituents commonly found in such environments, such as natural organic matter (NOM), function as light-absorbing species, generating hydroxyl radicals that act as non-selective oxidants which, in turn, react with nanomaterials [93]. Similarly, 2D materials such as TMDs, BP, and MXenes are prone to oxidation under ambient conditions, and various mitigation strategies have been considered [102,103].

Nanomaterials including 2D materials may also undergo microbial degradation [104]. Liu et al. [105] demonstrated that naphthalene-degrading bacteria isolated from a graphite mine had the ability to oxidize GO as well as rGO to varying degrees. Other investigators isolated a novel bacterial strain from soil samples which could use carbonaceous nanomaterials as the sole carbon source, and showed that GO, rGO, and single-walled CNTs underwent degradation upon 20 days of incubation with the bacteria [106]. Evidence was provided for an extracellular Fenton-like reaction wherein hydroxyl

radicals were generated by reduction of H_2O_2 involving the continuous cycling of Fe(II)/Fe(III). Similar findings were obtained using multi-walled CNTs [107]. Moreover, degradation of single-walled CNTs was investigated using bacteria of the genus *Shewanella* [108]. These facultative anaerobic bacteria produce Fe(II) by reducing Fe(III) under anaerobic conditions and H_2O_2 by reducing O_2 under aerobic conditions, thus evoking the Fenton reaction by switching between anaerobic and aerobic conditions. Single-walled CNTs were degraded by *Shewanella* over a period of 90 days during which a 24 h cycle consisting of a 21 h anaerobic phase and a 3 h aerobic phase was repeated 90 times in the dark in the presence of Fe(III) citrate [108]. Shen et al. [109] found that Ti_2C_3 MXenes could be oxidized by reactive oxygen species (ROS) produced by Gram negative as well as Gram positive bacteria, resulting in the formation of TiO_2 on the surface of the MXenes. Specifically, Ti_2C_3 MXenes stimulated bacterial respiration, leading to an increased generation of extracellular superoxide and the formation of H_2O_2 and hydroxyl radicals *via* a Fenton-like reaction.

Carbon-based nanomaterials, exemplified by CNTs and GO, may cause a shift in the gut microbiome (so-called dysbiosis) coupled with a ‘metabolic inflammation’ response [110]. Moreover, microbial fermentation of CNTs and GO in the gut was suggested to result in the incorporation of carbon from these nanomaterials into organic compounds (i.e., short-chain fatty acids) produced by the gut microbiome [111]. These compounds may, in turn, exert a multitude of effects on the host, in the gut and beyond. Biodegradation by insects has also been documented. Hence, biodegradation of GO was documented in mealworms, the larval form of the yellow mealworm beetle, and the microbiome residing in the gut of the mealworms was found to play a crucial role [112]. The authors found that twenty mealworms could ‘digest’ a film (1.5×1.5 cm) comprised of superimposed layers of GO in 15 days. For comparison, degradation of polyethylene (PE) was shown in waxworms (larvae of the wax moth), and some authors suggested that this was accomplished by PE-degrading bacteria in the gut of the waxworms [113], while others have shown that the gut microbial communities of caterpillars are not required [114]. More recent work disclosed that a family of proteins known as hexamerins are key factors in PE degradation [115]. However, to our knowledge, there are no studies on the biodegradation of ENMs by these ‘plastivores’.

White-rot fungi have evolved the ability to ‘digest’ all the major structural components of wood including hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin whereas brown-rot fungi can only break down hemicellulose and cellulose. The white-rot fungi are endowed with a wide array of degradative enzymes including the high redox-potential peroxidases (lignin peroxidases, manganese peroxidases, and versatile peroxidases) and laccases [116]. Early work demonstrated white-rot fungi-mediated degradation of C_{60} fullerene, the hydroxylated form of fullerene, resulting in the decomposition into CO_2 after 32 weeks [117]. Other investigators found that oxidized and reduced GO nanoribbons were completely and partially degraded by lignin peroxidase, respectively [118]. Several other studies have addressed the interactions between GBMs and white-rot fungi [119–121]. Hence, white-rot fungi were able to oxidize FLG to a GO-like material, and the authors concluded that FLG released into the environment would likely be oxidized by soil microflora [121]. Furthermore, laccases, not lignin peroxidase, emerged as the predominant degradative enzymes responsible for the degradation of GO [122]. This is notable as laccases are ubiquitous enzymes found in plants, fungi, and bacteria [123], unlike lignin peroxidase, which is restricted to a highly specialized group of fungi. Thus, both bacterial and fungal ENM degradation has been documented. It would be of interest to learn whether a consortium of bacteria and fungi might be more effective.

7. Biodegradation: implications for nanomedicine

The activity of any drug or nanomaterial is dependent on the drug or nanomaterial absorption, distribution, metabolism, and elimination (ADME) in the human body [124]. Therefore, the degradability and/or

excretability of nanomaterials and other advanced materials are key parameters in the (future) performance of such materials in the clinic.

Nanomaterials and other advanced materials including 2D materials are promising candidates for theranostics, the combination of therapeutics and diagnostics [125]. The present review has mainly focused on pristine or non-functionalized materials with a few notable exceptions, e.g., PEG- or PVP-modified, and BSA- or HSA-complexed ENMs. However, surface functionalization is a promising approach to enhance the biocompatibility of nanomaterials manufactured for biomedical applications [126]. Functionalization can also be exploited for tumor cell targeting of drug delivery vehicles and/or immune cell targeting with the purpose of promoting biodegradation [127]. The key is to control the biodegradation such that it happens in the right place at the right time. Degradation of a nanocarrier before it reaches its designated target tissue is of little use. Moreover, premature degradation of nanomaterials envisioned as scaffolds in tissue engineering would be counterproductive. Thus, design principles for the controlled biodegradation of nanomaterials and other advanced materials are needed.

The editors of *The Lancet* cautioned 18 years ago that “the unknown and under-researched health effects of nanotechnologies make it unwise to draw any concrete conclusions about their long-term safety” [128]. Likewise, we currently lack a solid understanding of the potential long-term effects of graphene and other emerging 2D materials on human health, and research efforts should be intensified to address this lest the perceived ‘risk’ and lack of regulation of these novel materials quell innovation. Understanding and controlling the biodegradation profile is a key step in this direction.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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